

The purpose of this review essay is for the NASA Earth Science Division to have a better understanding of Persistent Identifiers and how they help make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (aka FAIR). The essay was written to support the NASA Earth Science Data System Working Group's "Overview of Community FAIR Practices" (<https://doi.org/10.5067/DOC/ESCO/ESDSWG-0001V1>).

Persistent Identifiers in FAIR-Data Infrastructure

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Introduction

The persistent, unambiguous identification and location of (meta)data objects is now recognized as a necessary and central component of modern data infrastructure, especially in an interdisciplinary context (Klump et al. 2015; Klump et al. 2017; Wittenburg & Strawn 2018). Science builds on past work, and data available today from specific organizations in specific ways may still be very important long after transitory details of ownership, data formats, and access protocols have changed. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) allow us to add layers of abstraction that survive rapid technical change and changing access details and allow us to reconstruct past scientific workflows.

To that end, PIDs are a major component of the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). They are explicitly mentioned in three of the fifteen principles and their use is implied in several other principles. The use of PIDs is also required by NASA's new information policy, SPD-41a (NASA SMD, 2022) and the 2022 OSTP Memo on "Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research"¹. The application of PIDs to enhance data sharing and reuse has also been a major focus of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) (Lannom 2014), but unfortunately, it has been more difficult than anticipated (Klump et al. 2017; Wittenburg & Strawn 2018).

Oddly, PIDs are not explicitly defined in the original Wilkinson et al. (2016) description of the FAIR principles. In this document we adopt the National Science and Technology Council Definition - "A persistent identifier is a digital identifier that is globally unique, machine resolvable and processable, and with an associated metadata schema"² that identifies an entity (e.g., individual researcher, digital research object) in perpetuity and is used to disambiguate as well as build associations between entities.

¹ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/08-2022-OSTP-Public-Access-Memo.pdf>

² <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/010422-NSPM-33-Implementation-Guidance.pdf>

Background and Challenges

PIDs are increasingly used to try and address many different concerns and issues. They are perhaps best known as a key component for digital citation to literature, data, and software, but they may also underpin fundamental data frameworks such as linked data (Berners Lee 2006) or major NASA data systems like the Planetary Data System. Moreover, a core purpose of PIDs is to enable linking between the various objects of formal discourse (articles, data, software, people, instruments, etc.) (Mayernik, Phillips, and Nienhouse 2016).

In this essay, I focus on identifying the object (the noun) as opposed to its link or relationship to other objects (the verb), while recognizing that relationships between objects can sometimes contextualize and thereby define the objects (Mayernik, Phillips, and Nienhouse 2016, Parsons and Fox 2018a).

It can be confusing and complex, but ideally, if data and other research artifacts are unambiguously identified and located for machines to access them, we can address basic issues such as providing scholarly credit, measuring research impact, enabling reproducible workflows, and tracking provenance to build trust. PIDs are a first step toward data integration and interoperability, yet at an operational level, repository and other infrastructure managers and data stewards still struggle with when they should assign PIDs and to what “objects”. Managers are often confronted by routine questions of granularity and versioning: Which collection of files gets a DOI for citation? Who decides? Does this minor change require the need for a new DOI? Do I assign a PID to each file or query to my database? As new objects and identities are created with analysis, which of these must be captured? The result, the method, or both? Can more than one PID point to the same object? What does “the same” mean? Will the choice of identifier technology affect any of these decisions? There are few basic guidelines to aid in these decisions even within, let alone across, disciplines.

Even where practices are becoming firmly established like data citation in the scientific literature (Data Citation Synthesis Group 2014; Starr et al. 2015; ESIP Stewardship Committee 2019), there is still confusion around the particulars and a need to better separate concerns like reference, credit, provenance, and impact (Parsons & Fox 2014, Parsons, Jones, and Duerr 2019, Klump et al. 2021). For example, data journals were created to encourage data citation but in some ways they have confused the issue. Often there are two PIDs for a data set: one for the detailed data description in the journal, another for the actual data. These two resources have very different content, different machine access protocols, and even different authors. So what is the authoritative object? Which should be cited? When? Software citation is even more inchoate and uncertain (Smith et al. 2016; Katz and Chue Hong 2018). Meanwhile, leading journals require data and software citation, but they hedge their bets by also requiring human readable “data availability statements” (Stall et al. 2018). Unlike with a journal article, the machine resolution of a PID is not accepted as an authoritative reference unless it is accompanied by a human readable explanation. Defining the boundaries of an object can depend on its origins, management, and use (Mayernik, Phillips, and Nienhouse 2016).

The community needs to develop an understanding of how and when different practitioners actually make decisions on the identity and permanence of data objects. We need basic guidelines to reduce the decision risk for data stewards and infrastructure and repository developers and to accelerate interdisciplinary data interoperability.

Ideally, PIDs work to allow machines and humans to understand **which** digital object is in question (name), **where** it is (location), and **what** it is (category or type). These are very fundamental questions necessary to enabling broad and repeated access to data, but each of these questions is surprisingly fraught and complex. They are interdependent, and the answers are situational and sometimes ephemeral. Data infrastructure development is at a key point of evolution in the application and use of PIDs. The community currently works through controversies amongst competing systems and approaches in the development of the inter-networks which characterize mature infrastructure (Edwards et al., 2007).

Overall, answering the basic questions often raises more questions. Which, where, and what are defined by **how** and **why** within a **context** (Figure 1). The community needs to better understand the nature of the boundaries, overlaps, and intersections between these fundamental questions in order to define design and methodological principles for creating interdisciplinary data infrastructure.

Figure 1. The overlaps, intersections, and boundaries of identity.

Current State of Play

Types of Identifier Systems – addressing the which and where

Authority- Based IDs

Many existing identifier schemes³ meet the requirements in the NSTC definition above using what we might call authority-based identifiers, which separate the identity of an object from its location and are maintained in trusted registries. Current PID systems are a logical extension of long-established organizational systems. At one level, the concept is simple. It is a matter of keeping track of assets — a fundamental preoccupation of civilization, done for centuries by creating registries of the name and location of individual assets—people, land, food, books, machine parts, unique artifacts, etc. Modern, digital persistent identifier schemes accomplish the same thing for distributed digital assets. They provide a trusted registry of the name and location of digital objects. More specifically, they provide coordinated, distributed and centralized registries managed by trusted organizations who negotiate registrations with authorities responsible for the digital objects being registered and then provide an (optional) mechanism to locate and access the object (i.e., resolve the identifier).

Examples of these systems include, but are not limited to:

- The Handle, which underpins many services including the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) broadly used in scientific publishing and citation. Handles are managed by the Digital Object Naming Authority which manages a global resolver, handle.net.
- The Archive Resource Key (ARK), a highly-distributed, open system, which supports many research institutions, archives, and museums and provides some unique resolution and metadata features.⁴ n2t.net is a global resolver for ARKs and other PIDs but ARK creators are free to create their own local resolvers.
- identifiers.org is another resolver for registered URIs or Compact URIs broadly used in the life sciences community.

Hakala (2010)⁵ provides a more comprehensive overview of the different authority-based identifier systems, their background, and how they compare to so-called Cool URIs⁶. I do not discuss Cool URIs here because I do not believe they adequately address how access protocols change over time (same with “Persistent URLs” or PURLs⁷). Hakala wades more deeply into that debate. The ARK website also offers an opinionated but useful assessment of the different identifier schemes.

³ The US Library of Congress provides a lengthy list of identifier schemes: <https://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/identifiers.html>. The ESIP science-on-schema.org group decided to recommend the use of the [identifiers.org vocabulary](http://identifiers.org/vocabulary) as the source for standard URIs for identifier schemes: <https://github.com/ESIPFed/science-on->

⁴ <https://arks.org/about/>

⁵ There is an updated and more extensive version of this document available online, but it is only available in Finnish with no current plans to translate it: <https://www.doria.fi/handle/10024/182030>

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/cooluris/>

⁷ <https://purl.archive.org/>

The PIDs from these systems are often expressed as, or are based on, a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI). Somewhat confusingly, a URI is used to ‘identify a resource’, yet the definition says a URI can be a locator (where), a name (which), or both (Internet Engineering Task Force RFC 3986). Uniform Resource Names (URNs) are a type of URI which are location-independent, persistent identifiers for information resources. There are multiple URN namespace authorities, including ISBN, but currently no global resolution services. This remains an active area, and two proposed RFCs were published in 2017 — 8141 and 8254. PIDs address the concepts of name and location separately albeit registered under one identifier string. The key is that these systems include a managed resolution service. PIDs can be and often are URIs and may serve as URNs but the structure for maintaining the naming and location resolution service is what makes the identifier “persistent” as both a name and a locator or what Paskin (2000) calls “actionable identifiers”.

So we are essentially using the same organizational model that we have used for centuries, but some special challenges have emerged in the identification of digital objects. These challenges are especially difficult in research, where the objects we want to track closely and share broadly, like data and software, tend to be dynamic, specialized, and subject to interpretation. Moreover, “location” is somewhat of a misleading concept in a networked or cloud environment. For example, PID registries provide a mechanism to maintain the ‘web addresses’ or locations for data, but many data assets are actually associated with more than one URL, or FTP site, or cloud service endpoint. Indeed, an “object” may not even exist until a user creates a query that pulls data from multiple sources to create the object (Rauber et al. 2021). Location is often a surrogate for other issues like ownership or authority. Generally, what we really want from a PID

is a point of access, and that ‘point’ could very well be a highly distributed system, moving around even as we use it. In the relatively simple use case of citation of data in scientific literature, recommended practice is to use ‘landing pages’ to create one location to point to all the relevant information (Starr et al. 2015; ESIP Stewardship Committee 2019). But which elements comprise the relevant information? at what granularity are they presented? through which protocol? To answer the question of where, we must answer which (see box).

A Further Complication with “Which”

To answer which, we need to address the issues of oneness and sameness — something that even Aristotle grappled with (White 1971). It is fairly straightforward to determine the oneness or uniqueness of a digital object through checksums, Universal Numeric Fingerprints, or other content-based identifiers but this is rarely done outside an archival context. Instead data users rely on the perceived integrity of the provider (the location) as a proxy for validating that an object is the one it claims to be (again conflating where and which). Sameness or equivalence is more challenging.

The concept is reasonably well understood with physical objects, for example, the interchangeability rule for part numbers (PDXpert 2018) or the “work” vs. “item” distinction for books (e.g. Moby-Dick as a conceptual entity vs. the Denver Public Library’s copy of the 1998, Oxford University Press edition of Moby-Dick) (Maxwell 2007). It is much more complicated with digital objects that require unambiguous, detailed interpretation by machines, especially for reproducible science. Are two formats of a data object (e.g., a shapefile vs. an ASCII file) scientifically interchangeable? That is a much harder question to answer.

Klump et al. (2021) propose a framework, including core principles, for how we can conceive of different versions or representations of a ‘data set’. This deserves close consideration by repositories and data providers. Nonetheless, none of the current identifier schemes address this basic question of “scientific equivalence” (Duerr et al. 2011), nor can they in any absolute sense (Paskin 2003).

Content-based IDs

Some data managers now look to content-based identifiers (i.e., cryptographic-hash-based IDs) “to identify exact copies of digital data, ideally without relying on third parties and external administrative processes. These content-based identifiers can be deployed and resolved in peer-to-peer environments like the InterPlanetary File System (IPFS)⁸ and Dat⁹. There is an established system called Qri¹⁰ (query) which allows users to reference, browse, download, create, fork, and publish data sets with a broad network of peers in IPFS. Furthermore, Dat includes public-key technology to provide assurance on the source of the data and any changes that may have occurred. These approaches are still not well-suited to the massive volumes of streaming data [typical for NASA]. Nonetheless, these approaches show great promise. In related work, Bolikowski et al. (2015: 281) use the concepts of blockchain and version control systems like Git to propose a distributed system for maintaining long-term resolvability of persistent identifiers. They argue that the ‘system should be agnostic with respect to referent type (data sets, source codes, documents, people) and content delivery technology (HTTP, BitTorrent, Tor/Onion).’ (Parsons, Jones, and Duerr 2019, p.7)

Golodoniuc et al. (2017) further argue that decentralization of data registration, resolution, and delivery is necessary to increase system fault tolerance and trustworthiness. This warrants much more exploration.

It is important to note that content-based identifiers have quite different properties and applications from authority-based identifiers. Content-based identifiers and blockchain technologies can be useful for tracking provenance, precise data queries, and internal repository management concerns. Authority-based identifiers are being used for ensuring the social requirements necessary to maintain a persistent and managed access location (Di Cosmo et al. 2018), while those governance structures are only now being developed for distributed, content-based identifier systems. (Parsons, Jones, and Duerr 2019) In some cases, the systems can be combined by using hash-based identifiers in authority-based registries.

What

The ‘what’ or ‘resource type’ question is the most complex and context dependent of all. It is important to note that PIDs do not inherently identify the type of object they identify, but they may include or link to metadata addressing that question. The resource type may also be implied by the application or the registry.

⁸ <https://ipfs.io>

⁹ <https://dat.foundation>

¹⁰ <https://qri.io>

Sometimes, the technical details of type can be readily verified, for example with data formats. Anything beyond that, e.g., is this data about ice or water or both, requires declaring the type in some accountable way, e.g. “this is ice because...”. Type very much depends on who is defining the category, who is the audience, and the intent of the person who created the object. How are they evolving with the evolution of the data? Who are the unknown audiences? Given this complexity, ‘which’ and ‘where’ are sometimes used as a proxy for ‘what’ (This type of data set comes from this repository; or this type of asset is registered in this PID registry.)

The ESIP Data Citation Guidelines (ESIP Stewardship Committee 2019) adopted by NASA also note that, “humans and machines may interpret resource type differently. People can usually figure out a resource type for a particular use from other clues in the citation and the context in which it was cited. Machines need a precise understanding of resource type so they know what operations can be performed against the object (consider MIME types as an example). This suggests that we need not include resource type in the human readable text of the citation, and that repositories should provide structured information when resolving the identifier that allows machines to access and interpret the resource. This may be through a type registry or registered namespace or ontology. It may also be through a protocol with defined operations such as OpenDAP or the Digital Object Interface Protocol.

It is beyond the scope of this essay to address the many debates in category theory, but I do recognize that categorization has consequences (Bowker & Star 2000), and that we need not always draw bright lines. Given the diversity of perspectives, it may not be possible or desirable to clearly distinguish between types. Fortunately, we already have ways of representing fuzzy boundaries. Geography has long described imprecise and changing boundaries like coastlines and riverbanks. We can also make better use of associative and mapping links in SKOS (W3C’s Simple Knowledge Organization System) and rely more on late semantic binding (Lewis et al. 2006). We can use functionally defined or probabilistic weights in knowledge graphs. To do this, however, we must have a better understanding of the uses and perceptions of the objects in question and all the questions of identity. See more at (Parsons and Fox 2018b).

PIDs and Metadata

When creating authority-based PIDs, there is usually a requirement to provide some metadata in addition to the location of the object. Sometimes, the metadata in a PID record can be quite extensive and even redundant with other structured metadata. Moreover there is no universal agreement across registries on what should be required and how it should be represented. For example DOIs registered with DataCite have a different metadata schema than those registered with CrossRef even though those two registries collaborate and try to interconnect their respective PIDs.

An RDA Working Group developed a recommendation that lays out principles to guide in the identification of minimal information suitable for inclusion in the PID record. The goal is to curtail rapid growth of types and realize a long-term core of “universally” understood information “The information contained in a PID record is represented by a PID Kernel Information profile which must be publicly and globally available. For PID Kernel Information to be effective in stimulating

an ecosystem of data services, the number of different profiles of PID Kernel Information must be small and their content stable. The recommendation includes a draft profile with illustrating examples and cases for adoption in practice.” (Weigel et al. 2019). It could behoove NASA, in collaboration with other agencies, to define an initial profile suitable for Earth observation data.

Conclusion

Identity is a complex, multi-dimensional concept that is essential for data FAIRness and preservation as well as sustainable data infrastructure development. NASA cannot fully address all the issues involved and certainly cannot do so in isolation. NASA *can* continue to develop practical guidance on **how** to implement PIDs that considers the complexity of **which**, **where**, and **what** digital objects are important in a defined **context**.

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